

FACTORS AFFECTING CREDIT USE IN ÇORUM SMES

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SMEs (small and medium-sized enterprises), which gained importance in Turkey in the 1980s, account for a very high proportion of 99.9% of all enterprises. The influence of these numerically quite large enterprises on the economy needs to be increased.

Today, SMEs are indispensable elements of a country's economies due to their share in employment and production and their role in interregional balanced development. However, SMEs face many problems arising from both their structural characteristics and the economic environment.

The aim of this study is to examine the factors affecting the credit use of SMEs. In order to determine these factors, data was collected using a survey method through face-to-face interviews with 50 SME owners in Çorum province. Based on the data collected, the factors affecting the credit use of SMEs were revealed.

Keywords: *SME, Courm SMEs, Credit Use*

Introduction

In the global economic order where international competition intensifies, it is seen that companies tend to produce not only for national markets but also for international markets. These developments have made it necessary for companies to adapt to the global economy in order to be successful. In this regard, it becomes even more important for small and medium-sized enterprises to take their place and maintain their existence (Berger, 2005). SMEs, whose importance is increasing for economically, politically and socially developed and developing countries, are also of great importance for Turkey in terms of the employment opportunities they create, the share they receive from production and the preservation of socio-economic balance. SMEs fulfill an important function not only in economic life but also in social life (Surya at all, 2021, Kazanoğlu, 2023).

Since SMEs in Turkey are spread over a wide area, they are of great importance in terms of eliminating regional development differences, distributing ownership over a wide area, creating employment, protecting and balancing the middle class, and serving as schools in the field of vocational education (Akbaş and Bağcı, 2021, İşler, 2024). SME entrepreneurs' passion for ownership, desire for success, bold steps and willingness to invest are the basic political stability mechanisms. SMEs are important in both developed and developing countries, no matter how different their economic structures are. This importance increases especially in countries that face economic crises from time to time, such as Türkiye. SMEs, which contribute to the economy with their small and flexible structures, are on the world's agenda (Akyol, 2006, Azumah, 2019, Sajjad and Talat, 2024).

In today's world, where competition and change are very intense, SMEs, which provide the majority of employment and production, hold an important place in economies with their structures that can easily adapt to changes (Joel and Oguanobi, 2024, Aharoni, 2024). SMEs, which are the driving force of large enterprises, operate predominantly in the economies of developing countries because they need less financing than these

companies, employ less skilled workers, and are generally created according to the skills of entrepreneurs (Kindström at all, 2024, Zeng at all, 2011).

In SME banking, which is based on relationship banking and renews itself day by day, banks are trying to quickly respond to their demands and needs by trying to follow different policies on products and services in order to reach more SMEs. In this way, they aim to get a larger share from the sector by creating a profitable banking structure to increase their contribution to the economy and help SMEs grow. The main purpose of this study is to determine the factors affecting the credit use of SMEs in Çorum Organized Industrial Zone and to develop suggestions for solving the problems (Kizil at all, 2009, Hernández-Cánovas and Martínez-Solano, 2010, Ulaş, 2019, Kayhan and İslamoğlu, 2022).

This study consists of three parts. In the first section, information about the SME concept is given. In the second section, information is given about SMEs, SME banking and the concept of banking. In the third chapter, the factors affecting the credit use of SMEs in Çorum were examined and evaluated and a conclusion was reached.

SME Concept, Banking System and SME Banking

First of all, here is the definition of the SME concept and SME banking.

SME Concept

As in many developed and developing countries of the world, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) constitute the cornerstone of the economic structure in our country. Today, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) operate in the fields of trade, partnership and investment not only at the national but also at the global level, and continue their activities alongside large companies in international markets. With the help of technology, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) now have the opportunity to export more and grow faster than large companies (Pandya, 2012, Çatak, 2020).

SMEs perform important functions in social and economic life. They play an important role in increasing regional development and welfare levels. There is no generally accepted definition of SMEs in the world literature. Due to their structure, it is not possible to create a precise definition for these companies. Definitions of SMEs vary between countries and even between different regions and business sectors of the same country, depending on the level of industrialization, the business sectors to which the companies belong, the production methods used and the purpose intended by the definition. Various qualitative and quantitative criteria are taken into account when defining SMEs in countries around the world. A number of quantitative criteria such as the number of employees employed, work capacity, amount of working capital, annual turnover, total value of assets, size of the machinery park, amount of raw materials used, amount of energy consumed. The amount of wages and salaries paid to personnel in production, the added value created; Some qualitative criteria can be listed, such as the company's management style, the company's market situation, the area covered by the company, and whether all or most of the working capital belongs to the company owner. In general, quantitative criteria are used more to facilitate measurement in determining the size. According to these criteria, small business definitions vary from country to country, region to region and sector to sector. Definitions also change depending on changing economic conditions. (Müftüoğlu, 1989, Alpugan, 1994, Duygulu at all, 2008, Durst and Runar Edvardsson, 2012, Massaro at all, 2016).

Some of the definition of SME in Turkey:

Small and Medium Scale Industry Development and Support Administration Law (KOSGEB) regarding "definitions" states: "Industrial enterprises with 1-50 employees in the manufacturing sector are small industrial enterprises; Industrial companies with 51 to 150 employees are considered medium-sized industrial companies". Credit Guarantee Fund, which plays a role in eliminating collateral problems in bank loans to SMEs, accepts companies with up to 250 employees as SMEs. According to the definition of the Ministry of Industry and Trade: Enterprises with 1-19 employees are small enterprises, enterprises with 20-99 employees are medium-sized enterprises, and enterprises with 100 or more employees are large enterprises.

SMEs, which constitute one of the cornerstones of the country's economy, have some advantages over large companies due to their characteristics. An entrepreneur who owns a small or medium-sized business has two main advantages when competing with large companies. These are: closer relationships with customers and employees and greater flexibility in marketing, production and service. SMEs offer more production and product diversity with less investment, react faster to changes in demand and overcome economic fluctuations and crises with less damage thanks to their flexible structures (Sultan, 2007, Cunningham, 2011, Orhan and Yalçın, 2022, Udegbunam, 2024).

Besides their advantages, SMEs also have some disadvantages. SMEs are important because they cannot work with high efficiency because they are small-

scale and dispersed, their export potential is low because they cannot produce in accordance with standards, they cannot be institutionalized and therefore have difficulty in obtaining resources, and their technical and sectoral knowledge is not sufficient. is insufficient and their competitiveness is weak due to all these reasons. This can be seen as a disadvantage (Esmer and Dayı, 2017, Al Bakri and Kisswani, 2024).

Banking System

Banks are institutions that carry out all kinds of transactions in areas such as capital, money, credit, investment and service provision and have control over the existing resources of the society. The main functions of banks are to channel funds to society and accelerate development efforts. Money trading, giving and receiving money with interest, intermediating payment, carrying out monetary transactions such as credit and foreign exchange in return for a fee, keeping money, valuable documents and goods in safes, making direct investments and giving loans to merchants and industrialists. Acting as an intermediary and assistant in import-export working in businesses, giving useful advice to clients on buying stocks and bonds, owning a home and buying insurance, providing foreign currency to travelers, providing loans to farmers and supporting co-operatives are all these basic functions of banks (Jo'rayev, 2024, Erturk and Solari, 2007).

The beginning of shopping among people and the exchange of goods they own with other goods they need has created the need for a means of payment. With the development of trade factors such as collecting money from buyers elsewhere, difficulties and dangers in transporting precious metals, storing the metals in reliable places, and the existence of relationships between the buyer who prefers credit and the seller who determines the price of the goods, were the factors in the emergence of cash banking. The first legal regulation of banking, which is an economic institution that accepts deposits, aims to use these deposits in the most efficient way in various loan transactions and regularly receives or gives loans, dating back to the period before Christ (Healey and Ilieva, 2007, Gürbüz at all, 2023). These legal regulations are;

- Monetary loans (lending)
- Goods deposits (goods deposits)
- Provisions regarding the commission agreement

were included.

SME Banking

Companies with insufficient equity capital have difficulty growing and continuing their activities. Studies have shown that such companies usually disappear within the first five years. Alternatively, bank loans impose significant costs on companies due to high real interest rates. One of the most important elements that SMEs need to continue to exist and grow despite their flexibility in the economy is financing. It can be seen that financing problems and the lack of professionalization of management cause other problems of SMEs and prevent them from perceiving the changes in the environment and developing new strategies. Financial institutions are not very willing to provide their own funds for the short-term resources that SMEs need (Chittenden at all, 1996, Özgün, 2024).

Various banks offer short-term business loans to SMEs. However, SMEs also face maturity, limit and interest rate problems in these loans. Their biggest problem is the collateral required to grant these loans. Financial institutions require high collateral to enter into credit relationships with companies they consider risky. This puts companies in a vicious circle. If a company does not add its profits to its capital and acquire real estate, its chances of getting a loan decrease or even disappear. In addition, in times of crisis, financial institutions are the first to stop lending and cancel existing loans. All of this exacerbates the financial difficulties of SMEs (Ma'aji, 2019, Ata at all, 2015).

Turkey is making significant progress in this regard by increasing its exports significantly every day. Looking at exports by main items, the main focus is on the textile and clothing, leather and leather goods, agricultural industrial products and agriculture and livestock sectors. Due to the constant change in consumer preferences in these segments, organizing as a small and medium enterprise is more flexible and economical in terms of production method than organizing as a large enterprise. The fact that the total exports of the mentioned segments correspond to 60-70% of the total exports of the country on average shows that the export potential of SMEs is quite high (Adıgüzel, 2020, Gürel at all, 2023).

A Research on the Factors Affecting Credit Use in Çorum SMEs

Purpose of the Research

SMEs have to use their own resources or get loans from banks in order to continue their activities. Since SMEs are generally established with limited equity, the importance of financing, especially through borrowing into the banking system, increases. Intensive and effective use of loans by Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises is very important for both the survival of SMEs and the sustainable economic development in the country. In this study, it was aimed to reach a conclusion by investigating the factors affecting credit use in Çorum SMEs.

Scope and Limits of the Research

The research was carried out by face-to-face interviews with the owners, senior managers or managers of 50 exporting SMEs operating in the Çorum Organized Industrial Zone, which employ up to 250 workers and were determined by the Çorum Chamber of Commerce and Industry to export, and answers were received from 50 SMEs. In the research, the answers given by the subjects were accepted as correct. It was assumed that the subjects participating in the research correctly and completely understood the questions asked to them.

Research Method and Sample

The research is based on survey management. The data required for the research was collected by face-to-face survey method. The face-to-face survey method is important in order to have a high response rate and to obtain a lot of information about the opinions and attitudes of the participants, as well as their economic, psychological and social structures. In determining the questions in the survey form, relevant literature and previous studies on this subject were taken into ac-

count. After the questions forming the survey were determined, they were applied to 10 businesses for testing. The final version of the survey form was created by making necessary corrections in line with the problems encountered in practice, the aims and hypotheses of the research. In the study, the entire universe was chosen as the sample mass. In order to evaluate the factors affecting the use of credit for the research topic, a total of 21 questions were asked and a survey was conducted as a result of face-to-face interviews with SMEs in the Organized Industrial Zone of Çorum province. Among the survey forms obtained from the study, 50 survey forms were considered as evaluable.

Demographic Information Obtained from the Research

According to the information obtained from the research, it was understood that 15 of the survey participants were college graduates, 26 were undergraduate and 9 were graduate graduates. It has been determined that Çorum SMEs consist of 30 businesses with 0-9 personnel, 5 businesses with 10-49 employees, and 15 businesses with 50-249 employees. It was determined that none of the businesses had 250 or more employees. 16 businesses with annual net sales revenue and annual financial balance sheet total of 0-3000000 TL, 29 businesses with 3000000 (not included) - 25000000 TL, 5 businesses with 25000000 (not included)-125000000 TL were identified. In the establishment phase of Çorum SMEs, the number of businesses with their own equity is 27, inheritance from the father is 1, capital received from family members is 9, the number of businesses started with capital obtained from relatives and friends is 7, the number of businesses started with bank loans is 39, and the number of businesses with other defined capital is 39. It was determined that the number of companies starting business was 4 enterprises. It is seen that 43 of the participants use credit and 7 of them do not use credit. It was determined that there were 8 businesses with a loan period of 0-6 months, 15 businesses with a loan period of 6 months-2 years, 18 businesses with a loan period of 2-5 years, and 23 businesses using loans with a maturity range of 5 or more.

Reasons for Using Credit in Çorum SMEs

According to the information obtained from the study, the reasons why businesses do not use loans are listed as follows;

4 businesses with sufficient equity capital,

The number of businesses that describe loan interest rates as high is 21,

The number of businesses that think the collateral conditions are harsh is 16,

The number of businesses stating that the number of creditors providing loans is insufficient is 3,

The number of businesses that gave reasons other than those listed was determined as 23.

The answers given by businesses to the question "What are the difficulties you encounter when getting a loan?" are;

The number of businesses claiming that their loan requests were not taken into consideration sufficiently is 2,

The number of businesses claiming that there is a waste of time between loan application and loan allocation is 27,

The number of businesses stating that they encountered collateral difficulties is 25 businesses.

The number of businesses that say the formalities are quite heavy is 10 businesses,

The number of businesses stating that there were reasons other than those listed above was determined as 15 businesses.

Looking at the answers to the question "Is the loan amount you received sufficient?"

According to the results obtained from the study, it was determined that 16 businesses found the loans they received sufficient.

It was determined that 34 businesses found the loan amount they provided insufficient.

Businesses were also asked for their opinions on the current credit system. To the question asked in this context, businesses asked;

2 businesses stated that they were not interested in loans.

The number of businesses stating that interest rates are high was 23 businesses.

27 businesses stated that the maturity granted to the allocated loans was short.

The number of businesses stating that the amount of credit allocated was low was 13 businesses.

It was determined that the number of businesses that stated that the loan amount was appropriate and in proportion to inflation was 8 businesses.

According to the information obtained from the study, data on the factors affecting the credit use of businesses;

27 businesses expressed the speed of banks in solving problems,

15 businesses expressing the bank's advertising activities,

The businesses that provide returns as personalized service were identified as 43 businesses.

37 businesses saying diversity of credit opportunities,

45 businesses that say banking services are provided quickly,

It was determined that there were 41 businesses that stated that the costs related to products and services were low.

Result and Conclusion

The aim of this study is to clarify the factors affecting the borrowing of 50 SMEs operating in Çorum province. The following conclusions were drawn from the findings of the research. It was found that the majority of companies use loans and most of these loans are provided by banks.

It was found that the majority of companies that do not use loans do not use loans because time is lost between applying for and receiving the loan. Other reasons for not taking loans are the high loan interest rates and collateral conditions. Most of the difficulties that companies face in taking loans are the difficulty of providing collateral and the burden of formality. It was seen that there are companies that say about the current

credit system that the loan terms are short, the interest rates are high and the loan amounts are low.

Companies often prefer to run their businesses with their available money and use long-term loans for long-term investments. The main reason for this is investments that will bring results and benefits in the long term. Investing all the capital at their disposal is risky, especially for SMEs. The more private companies that play a role in a country invest, the more the country will develop. 90% of companies use loans out of sheer necessity.

There is a close link between support for SMEs and employment. Complex and lengthy loan processes and loan costs encourage companies to forego taking loans and cutting jobs. By laying off the existing workforce or being unable to pay salaries above the minimum wage, employees are both dissatisfied and unhappy because they cannot be satisfied. As support for these companies increases, those who want to invest in entrepreneurial companies will come to the fore. The problem of collateral should be eliminated for SMEs.

Insufficient collateral is always a problem in loan applications from newly established small and medium-sized enterprises. The first degree mortgage required for medium and long-term investment loans discourages SME companies in particular from using these loans. In addition, SME companies have difficulty meeting the additional collateral banks require when they apply for additional loans as they expand their business. If companies use the loans they receive in the right places, their profitability can increase due to leverage.

Depending on the industry in which the companies are located, special loan packages should be prepared and representatives of commercial banks should present reasonable and innovative ideas to the companies. Additional expenses such as filing costs, appraisal fees and insurance fees that add to the cost of loans for SMEs should be kept to a minimum so that they can grow and create jobs. The documents required from the companies should be reduced depending on whether they are long-term customers of the bank or how many years they have been in the industry.

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